

Story Tellers Who Spin in Orbit of Space (Women in Space)

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Introduction

Now we can proudly say we have launched so many satellites to the space. We are waiting eagerly to buy a flat on the moon. We also are seeking for the ways to live in other planets. What is the basis of all those growth? What is the reason behind all those glories?

In the earlier days, mothers fed their babies by showing the sky and moon and telling the fantastic stories about the sky and the celestial bodies. That made them to think, imagine and develop on their creativity. That cheered them up to make the imagination to come alive. The beautiful story tellers have created valiant women who could travel to the space to orbit around the celestial bodies. Yes! It came true... Really we have to be proud to say that we have sent our powerful women to the space.

"As a Woman I have no country, as a Woman I want no country, as a woman my country is the whole world..." said Virginia Woolf.

But as a woman her country is not only the world, Of course it is the whole universe, the whole space! Yes it is...

The First Woman in Space

Now many countries are interested to send female astronaut to the space. Because they believe and understand that "The country will succeed by the potential and power of women". But few decades early, the people were not ready to send the women to the space. They always thought that women cannot withstand the psychological stresses of separation and isolation as men could do. The society was happy to keep their women in cozy comfort zone of that boundary, within the shade of the men as a father, brother and husband. There were lots of such boundaries needed to be broken for a woman to be an astronomer.

The woman, who dared not to remain just as story teller, but be the heroin of the story field. Yes, she desired to fly to the space. Of course she flew to space in 1963. She was the first female who went to the space. She did not restrict her role just to be a daughter

and wife alone but believed in her potential par excellence to create a history. She worked tirelessly to achieve it and hence she attained it. She flew like a silvery bird around the earth on Vostok 6 mission June 16, 1963. Her name is Valentina Tereshkova. She was a Soviet cosmonaut. She was born in 1937 in a rural place known as Maslennikovo in Tutayevsky District, Yaroslavl Oblast in central Russia. Tereshkova was a simple textile-factory assembly worker and an amateur skydiver before her recruitment as a cosmonaut. She had the pride of orbiting around the earth for 48 times. How amazing journey it is!

Many Who Followed Tereshkova

After Tereshkova, in 1982 another Soviet aviator Svetlane Savitskaya went to the space. That happened 19 years after Tereshkova. After these two brave women, many women were involved in space shuttle mission. Sally Ride was the first female astronaut. She was an American physicist. She was the third woman to fly in space. And she is the first American female who travelled to space.

In Later years, Women from many countries were involved in space mission programs. Most of them were from United States. Among the many nations, three countries namely United States, Russia and china showed great interest to send their women to space. Countries like India, Canada, United Kingdom and France contributed fairly to the space mission programs.

The first woman to command the International Space Station was Peggy Whitson, the NASA astronaut during Expedition 16 in April 2008. She became the maiden woman to command the space station twice when she took command of Expedition 51 in 2016. Having return from her final mission at the age of 57, she inherits the record for being the senior woman in space.

She has spent 665 days, 22 hours and 22 minutes in orbit over the span of three trips to the International Space Station. She had logged more hours in space than any U.S. astronaut and returned from her final trip to space in 2017.

During mission STS-41-G in 1984, Kathryn D. Sullivan, the NASA astronaut became the first American woman to do a spacewalk as she floated outside the space shuttle Challenger.

Helen Sharman, the British chemist became the first person to fly in space and first woman to visit the Mir space station in Soyuz TM-12 in 1991. NASA astronaut Mae Jemison took pride in being the first African-American woman to travel to space flew on space shuttle Endeavour in September 1992. Roberta Bondar was Canada's first female astronaut as she flew on the STS-42 space shuttle mission in 1992.

Chiaki Mukai who represented the National Space Development Agency of Japan (NASDA) was the first Japanese woman in space as she flew on the space shuttle Columbia during mission STS-65 in July 1994. She also holds record for the longest flight to date by a female astronaut.

Doctor Claudie Haigneré became the first and only French woman to travel to space when she flew to the Russian space station Mir in 1996. In 2001, she became the first European woman to visit the International Space Station.

Samantha Cristoforetti is the most recent woman to have returned from space in November 2014. She the first Italian woman to have entered space as a part of the Futura mission to ISS, and holds the record for longest single space flight by a woman (a whopping 199 days and 16 hours) and the record for the longest uninterrupted flight by a European astronaut.

Indian Women's Contribution

Kalpana Chawla was an India born American astronaut and specialist in space shuttle mission. Among the seven crew members who died aboard space shuttle Columbia disaster during mission STS-107, she was one. Sunita Williams is yet another woman of Indian origin but an American

astronaut who went to space. She was chosen as an astronaut by NASA in 1998 and is a veteran of two space missions Expeditions 14/15 and 32/33. She is presently training for the first post-certification mission of Boeing's Star liner spacecraft – the second crewed flight for that vehicle – and her third long duration mission aboard the International Space Station. Williams and her crewmates are working closely with Boeing to develop their new spacecraft systems, which will provide roundtrip crew transportation services to the International Space Station and, along with SpaceX's Crew Dragon, return the ability to launch humans into space from United States soil. In 2017, Shawna Pandya came into spotlight when it was announced that the Canadian citizen of Indian origin was going to be the third Indian woman to fly to space. The 33-year-old practicing physician based in Alberta, Canada, worked as a citizen-scientist astronaut with projects related to space like Possum and PHEOM, whose "ultimate goal is to send citizen-scientist astronauts to space".

The above three Indian originated women were sent by other nations on various space shuttle missions. Till today no female from India is sent to space. India has planned for its first manned space Gaganyaan mission by 2022. There is probability for woman to be employed in that particular mission. If India achieves this, we will be the fourth country to send human to space after Russia, United States and China.

But the team behind Gaganyaan has plenty of tasks left to tackle, including selecting and training crewmembers, perfecting a spacesuit design, preparing launch pads and developing the astronauts' expertise in bioscience. The government estimates the project could create 15,000 jobs, and it could cost the equivalent of about \$1.3 billion.

Challenges for Space Exploration

Space is more hostile to human life than the surface of the sea as the space has no air. Since there is no atmospheric pressure in space, human beings have difficulty to breathe. There is absence of pressure on the human body from the outside in space and there is outward pressure from our bodies. This imbalance of pressure would lead to a fatal end. Hence Spacecraft, space stations, and space suits will have to be sufficiently pressurized so that people inside them will have about the balanced atmospheric pressure on them that they have at sea level.

Light rays travel through space from the sun, but there is no light. If only light rays are reflected from something, it can be seen. The space is dark because there are no particles to reflect light rays. When an object such as a spacecraft enters space, the light rays will be reflected from the craft. The craft will be a dazzling contrast to the dark space around it. An astronaut will have to be extremely cautious about protecting his eyes.

There is no heat in space as there is nothing to absorb the rays coming from the sun to produce heat. As the rays strike a spacecraft, some of the rays will be reflected from it. Some will be absorbed and turned into heat energy. The atmosphere protects the earth from the intense rays of the sun. In space there will be no such protection. The spacecraft will have designed in such a manner that it reflects some of the rays or else it will be impossible for man to remain alive. The craft will have to absorb just enough rays for comfort.

Space has no material through which sound waves can travel. This means there are no sound waves so there is no sound except inside the craft or the space suit. However, radio waves can travel through space, so communication will probably not be a great problem.

As a spacecraft reaches the particular point, the passengers and everything in the craft including the craft will become weightless. When an object is weightless, it can no longer be dropped, but even a slight push on it would move it. It would keep moving until it encounters a barrier such as the side of the craft. Therefore, objects such as furniture and equipment will have to be firmly

anchored to the floor of the spacecraft. Magnetic shoes have been suggested as one way to anchor men to the spacecraft. The disadvantage to this is that a man's feet would be anchored firmly, while all the other parts of his body would be weightless.

Since there is no atmosphere in space as in the earth's atmosphere which protects humans from different kinds of rays, Spacecraft, space stations, and space suits will have to be designed to protect people from harmful rays from the sun.

When meteors enter the earth's atmosphere, friction caused by air makes them so hot that they soon burn up. In space, there is no air to cause friction. Meteors are moving like stray bullets in space, whizzing by at tremendous speeds, in no definite paths. A meteor no bigger than the period at the end of this sentence, travelling at its speed of twenty to sixty miles per second, could easily puncture a space suit, craft, or station.

A spacecraft will need to be very powerful to carry the craft through the earth's atmosphere, beyond the earth's great gravitational pull and into space. The hardest problem has been to find a way to carry all the fuel required to lift a rocket against the earth's gravitational pull. Scientists have used multistage rockets for this purpose.

Another problem in the construction of spacecraft is how to land them. The friction of air would cause a returning craft to become a flaming meteor and burn up in seconds. Spacecraft will have to be built so that they can re-enter our atmosphere slowly. As they enter, they will need to circle gradually downward. By circling round and round, they will descend into the thicker air near the earth more slowly. Friction of air will not be as great, and the spacecraft will not become as hot.

Since spacecraft will not be able to carry all the fuel they need for a trip, space stations will probably be built where craft can refuel. These space stations will probably be constructed somewhere beyond three hundred miles above the earth. They will revolve around the earth in a fixed orbit, just as the moon does. At a distance of 1,050 miles beyond the earth, such a space station will have to go around the earth at a speed of almost 16,000 miles per hour. At this speed, its centrifugal force will just equal the earth's gravity. It will remain in its orbit.

Hope and Fear of Future Women Astronauts

Apart from the challenges mentioned above, Some critics wondered how women could handle menstruation in microgravity, and whether exposure to radiation would affect fertility.

A shift came in the late 1970s, when NASA was preparing to launch the first mission of the Space Shuttle program. The shuttle could carry more passengers than ever, which meant not everyone onboard had to be a military pilot. Scientists and doctors were welcome, too. NASA selected its first female astronauts in 1978, and Ride made her historic trip five years later.

In the years since, research has shown that women may be more susceptible to certain health risks than men in space. Women are more likely to get urinary tract infections, and have a lower threshold for exposure to radiation, due to the risk of breast, ovarian, and uterine cancers. None of these factors have anything to do with their brains, temperaments, or abilities—the qualities that critics once cited as disqualifying.

To date, nearly 60 American women have flown in space. The latest class of NASA astronauts, selected in 2013, includes four women and four men.

The immense power endowed woman awaits to create history and milestones in her advancement in space science.

Conclusion

The greatest and marvelous way to shape the society, to develop the country and to change the world, is very simple. Of course, it is to realize and respect the values of the women, to cheer up them, to achieve their goal, to reach the sky. Then they will shine like real stars bright and beautiful travelling in the silvery spacecraft from earth to the space.

She...! Seeming to be calm,
Firing like a flame, to achieve her aim!!
Opening the door way to fame of Fame!!!

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